

Measurement of Free-Carrier Density in a 1.2 kV SiC Schottky Diode under Overstress Conditions

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Abstract— For the first time, the Internal InfraRed-Laser Deflection (IIR-LD) method is applied to successfully measure the carrier density profile in a 1.2 kV SiC Schottky diode under overcurrent. This overstress induces high injection level into the drift region at the junction termination extension (PiN diode activation). Novel strategies compensate for key issues in IIR-LD data; i.e., decoupling temperature and carrier density, and correcting for the effect of the beam's larger diameter ($\sim 16 \mu\text{m}$) relative to the inspected layer ($13 \mu\text{m}$ thick). In the drift region, experimental results match simulations, showing carrier densities ranging from 2.73×10^{16} to $3.47 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. Moreover, substrate data reveal temperature-driven dopant ionization.

Keywords—Free-carrier density, temperature, depth-resolved analysis, incomplete dopant ionization, refractive index gradient.

I. INTRODUCTION

Enhancing power semiconductor ruggedness by design is crucial for improving reliability in power electronic systems [1], [2]. This process involves analyzing die-level phenomena that limit the device operation under stress. In this context, free-carrier distribution plays a key role, as it is responsible for the onset of destructive mechanisms, like current crowding [3]-[5]. Technology Computer Aided Design (TCAD) simulations are employed to tailor free-carrier distribution and enhance device ruggedness [6], [7]. Unfortunately, the accuracy of these results is often limited in wide-bandgap (WBG) devices due to incomplete parameter databases, high computational costs, and complex 3D effects [8]-[10]. Consequently, experimental methods are required to refine TCAD simulations. To address this, Internal InfraRed Laser Deflection (IIR-LD) has emerged as a promising technique [11]. IIR-LD enables depth-resolved measurements of carrier density profiles [12]-[16]. Recently, in a silicon carbide (SiC) device, IIR-LD outperformed free-carrier absorption, the mainstream method for free-carrier density determination [11]. Despite this, two challenges remain. First, no approach is currently available to decouple thermal and electrical effects in the IIR-LD data. Second, compensating for the beam diameter's effect in measurements is not addressed. This is critical for WBG devices, as the thickness of the inspected layer is comparable to or smaller than the laser spot size.

In this work, a solution is proposed to effectively process IIR-LD data for free-carrier profile measurement in WBG devices. To demonstrate this, a 1.2 kV SiC Schottky diode under overcurrent stress is used as a test vehicle. Specifically, the carrier density profile at its edge termination region is measured and compared to TCAD simulations. This work is structured as follows. First, a description of the IIR-LD setup, test vehicle, experimental conditions, and performed simulations is provided. Second, a strategy for extracting the free-carrier density is presented, addressing electrothermal decoupling and multiple-ray issues. Third, the proposed

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Fig. 1. IIR-LD probing setup representation at a given depth (x_0, y_0) . approach is assessed. Finally, conclusions are drawn.

II. METHODOLOGY DETAILS

A. IIR-LD Setup and Physical Basis

In Fig. 1, the experimental setup for conducting IIR-LD measurements is illustrated. A collimated $1.3 \mu\text{m}$ wavelength laser beam passes through the device under test (DUT) die, striking perpendicularly on its two opposite sidewalls. The laser is focused at the center of the device in the z -axis using the LE_1 lens. A micro-positioning stage with sub-micron resolution enables precise movement of the probing laser to the x_0 and y_0 positions for inspection. When the device is biased and current flows through it, free-carriers are injected into its drift region creating a free-carrier density gradient $\vec{\nabla}C(\vec{r}, t)$. This biasing also induces self-heating, which results in a temperature gradient $\vec{\nabla}T(\vec{r}, t)$. Together, these gradients give rise to a refractive index gradient $\vec{\nabla}n(\vec{r}, t)$ due to plasma-optical and thermo-optical effects, as described by

$$\vec{\nabla}n(\vec{r}, t) = \left(\frac{\partial n}{\partial C}\right)_T \vec{\nabla}C(\vec{r}, t) + \left(\frac{\partial n}{\partial T}\right)_C \vec{\nabla}T(\vec{r}, t), \quad (1)$$

where $(\partial n/\partial C)_T$ and $(\partial n/\partial T)_C$ represent the plasma-optical and thermo-optical coefficients of SiC, respectively. The refractive index gradient causes the probing laser beam to deflect. A second lens LE_2 directs the deflected beam along the z -axis, striking on a four-quadrant photodetector. This detector generates two output signals, $V_{out,y}(x_0, y_0, t)$ and $V_{out,x}(x_0, y_0, t)$ corresponding to the deflections along the y - and x -axes, respectively, at the beam incidence depth (x_0, y_0) . Based on the setup geometry and the paraxial approximation, $\nabla_i n(x_0, y_0)$ relates to $V_{out,i}(x_0, y_0, t)$ as [12]

$$\nabla_i n(x_0, y_0, t) = \frac{V_{out,i}(x_0, y_0, t)}{k'_{i_0} \cdot f_{LE_2} \cdot L \cdot \left(\frac{L}{2f_{LE_2} n_0} + 1\right)}, \quad (2)$$

where the subscript i refers to the y - and x -axes. k'_{i_0} is an experimental calibration coefficient determined for each inspection depth, L is the device length, n_0 is the SiC's refractive index, and f_{LE_2} is the focal length of the LE_2 lens.

Fig. 2 (a) Side view of the analyzed device. (b) Doping profile of the device's JTE. (c) $j_{Bias} - V$ static characteristic. (d) Simulated and measured $I_{Bias}(t)$.

B. Test Vehicle Description

As a DUT, a 1.2 kV Schottky SiC diode (1.6 mm \times 1.6 mm active region) with an edge termination based on Junction Termination Extension (JTE) is used as a test vehicle. In such devices, current crowding phenomena are expected in the termination region due to the PiN diode-like structure present. Fig. 2 (a) shows a side view of the device structure, and Fig. 2 (b) its doping profile in the JTE, used in the simulations of II.C. The drift region is 13 μ m thick with an n-type doping level of 4×10^{15} cm $^{-3}$, a 0.5 μ m-thick n-type buffer layer of 1×10^{18} cm $^{-3}$ and an n $^{+}$ -type substrate with a dopant density of 7.5×10^{18} cm $^{-3}$. The Schottky contact is made of titanium. The p-type JTE is implemented via an aluminum ion implantation at 300 $^{\circ}$ C with a dose of 1.1×10^{13} cm $^{-2}$, followed by post-annealing at 1600 $^{\circ}$ C for 30 mins. Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (SIMS) measurements determined that the doping peak in the JTE is 9.9×10^{16} cm $^{-3}$. The field plate is implemented with SiO $_2$. Before IIR-LD measurements, the die lateral walls are polished to enhance transmissivity, achieving RMS surface roughness below 60 nm. The device is then soldered onto a power substrate, and the contacts are established using aluminum bonding wires.

C. Experimental Conditions and TCAD Simulations

To bias the device under overcurrent conditions, it is placed at room temperature on a heat sink and subjected to a pulsed current density j_{Bias} ranging from 215 to 330 A/cm 2 . The experimental data is presented in Figs. (c) and (d). The static characteristic $j_{Bias} - V$ illustrates the activation of the parasitic PiN diode (bipolar conduction) and the onset of current crowding at 2.7 V, with the slope change of the data. Fig. 2 (d) shows the value of the overstress current I_{Bias}

(8.4 A, i.e., 328 A/cm 2) and its stabilization instant t_0 (15.6 μ s), indicating the onset of the electrical steady-state. For assessment, the experimental results are compared to TCAD simulations of the DUT [17]. The doping profile shown in Fig. 2 (b), and conditions of incomplete ionization, commonly present in SiC, are used. Electrode resistances are adjusted to align with the device's $j_{Bias} - V$ static characteristics and overcurrent pulse I_{Bias} , as shown in Figs. 2 (c) and (d), respectively.

III. IIR-LD DATA PROCESSING FOR $\nabla_i C$ EXTRACTION

A. Electrothermal Decoupling

First, the contribution of $\bar{\nabla}C(x_0, y_0, t)$ to $\bar{\nabla}n(x_0, y_0, t)$ is extracted as follows. To obtain $\nabla_i C(x_0, y_0, t)$, the following relation is assumed [18]

$$I_{Bias}(t) = K(x_0, y_0) \left[\bar{\nabla}C(x_0, y_0, t) - \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial n} \right)_T \delta_E(x_0, y_0) \right], \quad (3)$$

where $K(x_0, y_0)$ and $\delta_E(x_0, y_0)$ are constants related to the injection area and material parameters, and the drift current at (x_0, y_0) , respectively. In the on-state, $\delta_E(x_0, y_0)$ remains constant, as the drift component forms almost instantly, being in practice time-independent [18]. Using (1) and (3), this relation is inferred

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_i n_T(x_0, y_0, t) + \delta_E(x_0, y_0) \\ = \nabla_i n(x_0, y_0, t) - \left(\frac{\partial n}{\partial C} \right)_T [I_{Bias}(t)/K(x_0, y_0)]. \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

$K(x_0, y_0)$ is calculated by scaling $I_{Bias}(t)$ to $\nabla_i n(x_0, y_0, t)$ at t_0 [$I_{Bias}(t = t_0)$, see Fig. 2 (d)]. Using (4), $\nabla_i n_T(x_0, y_0, t) + \delta_E(x_0, y_0)$ is determined. To compensate for $\delta_E(x_0, y_0)$, an offset is subtracted from $\nabla_i n_T(x_0, y_0, t) + \delta_E(x_0, y_0)$, ensuring waveform continuity, monotonicity, and sign consistency to obtain $\nabla_i n_T(x_0, y_0, t)$.

In a second phase, $\nabla_i n_T(x_0, y_0, t)$ is fitted to an equation describing the time diffusion of a constant heat flux in a semi-infinite medium [19], i.e.

$$\nabla_i n_T(x_0, y_0, t)|_{fit} = \mathcal{A}(x_0, y_0) \operatorname{erfc} \left(\frac{\mathcal{B}(x_0, y_0)}{\sqrt{t}} \right), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathcal{A}(x_0, y_0)$ and $\mathcal{B}(x_0, y_0)$ are the fitting parameters at (x_0, y_0) . With $\nabla_i n_T(x_0, y_0, t)|_{fit}$, $\nabla_i n_C(x_0, y_0, t)$ is found as

$$\nabla_i n_C(x_0, y_0, t) = \nabla_i n(x_0, y_0, t) - \nabla_i n_T(x_0, y_0, t)|_{fit}. \quad (6)$$

B. Large Beam Diameter Compensation

When the beam diameter is comparable to the thickness of the inspected layer, the probing laser can be considered a Gaussian-distributed ray bundle [15], [16]. In this case, the measured deflections result from the sum of individual ray deviations, each weighted by its respective intensity. Consequently, the measurement provides an effective index gradient $\nabla_i n(x_0, y_0, t)$ at the depth (x_0, y_0) . According to [15] and [16], $\nabla_i n(x_0, y_0, t)$ is related to the gradient of the refractive index of a single ray $[\nabla_i n'(x, y, t)]$ at (x_0, y_0) as

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_i n(x_0, y_0, t) \\ = \frac{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx \int_0^{w_B} \nabla_i n'(x, y, t) e^{-\frac{2(x_0-x)^2}{w_x^2(z)}} e^{-\frac{2(y_0-y)^2}{w_y^2(z)}} dy}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx \int_0^{w_B} e^{-\frac{2(x_0-x)^2}{w_x^2(z)}} e^{-\frac{2(y_0-y)^2}{w_y^2(z)}} dy}, \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$w_i(z) = w_{0i} \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{l_i z \lambda}{n_0 w_{0i}^2 \pi} \right)^2}, \quad (8)$$

w_{0i} is the beam waist in the i -axis, l_i is the beam ideality factor, and λ is the laser wavelength. In (7), the y integration limits account for the thickness of the drift region w_B , as the laser beam is not transmitted above and below it. Equation (7) is discretized as

$$\nabla_i n(x_{0,j}, y_{0,m}, t) = \frac{1}{\mathcal{P}(x_{0,j}, y_{0,m})} \times \sum_{j=1}^{h_j} \sum_{m=1}^{n_p} \left[\nabla_i n'(x_j, y_m, t) e^{-\frac{2(y_{0,m}-y_m)^2}{w_{y_{0,m}}^2(z)}} e^{-\frac{2(x_{0,j}-x_j)^2}{w_{x_{0,j}}^2(z)}} \right], \quad (9)$$

where the subscripts m and j iterate over all the $h_j \times n_p$ depths, and

$$\mathcal{P}(x_{0,j}, y_{0,m}) = \sum_{j=1}^{h_j} \sum_{m=1}^{n_p} \left[e^{-\frac{2(y_{0,m}-y_m)^2}{w_{y_{0,m}}^2(z)}} e^{-\frac{2(x_{0,j}-x_j)^2}{w_{x_{0,j}}^2(z)}} \right]. \quad (10)$$

To infer $\nabla_i n'(x_j, y_m, t)$, (9) is solved as a linear system using the Cramer's rule. To apply (9), $w_i(z)$ have been characterized and all parameters required in (8) and (9) found. Moreover, for each measurement, the radius of the laser beam at the detector [$w_{y_{0,m}}(z_d)$] is measured during the calibration deflection signal $V_{out,y}(x_{0,j}, y_{0,m})$ versus beam spot displacement on the photo-detector (y_d), i.e. [20]

$$V_{out,y}(x_{0,j}, y_{0,m}) = k'_{y_{0,m}} y_d = \frac{-20\sqrt{2/\pi}}{w_{y_{0,m}}(z_d)} y_d. \quad (11)$$

Finally, the mean beam radius inside the device at each depth ($\overline{w_{y_{0,m}}}$) is used in (9) (i.e., $w_{y_{0,m}}(z) = \overline{w_{y_{0,m}}}$) to determine $\nabla_i n'(x_j, y_m, t)$. Equation (11) applies also to the x -axis with variable names adapted accordingly.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To validate the novel approaches described in III, the DUT is subjected to I_{Bias} [see Fig. 2 (d)], which activates the PiN parasitic diode of the JTE termination. Under these conditions, this evaluation process aims to derive the free-carrier density profile at $t = t_r$ and $x_0 = x_{Edge}$ [see Fig. 2 (a), $C(x_{Edge}, y_0, t = t_r)$]; as the free-carrier density reaches the steady-state at t_r , and I_{Bias} is concentrated there. Moreover, $C(x_{Edge}, y_0, t = t_r)$ reaches a maximum and is symmetric along the x -axis. This simplifies (9)-(10) to depend only on y , while ensuring that the experimental results remain representative of the overstress condition. Next, each step leading to $C(x_{Edge}, y_0, t = t_r)$ is illustrated.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of the decoupling strategy, the approach in III.A is detailed in Fig. 3. Fig. 3 (a) illustrates the obtention of $(\partial n / \partial C)_T K^{-1}(x_{Edge}, y_0)$. It is calculated by dividing $\nabla_y n(x_{Edge}, y_0, t = t_0)$ by $I_{Bias}(t = t_0)$. Multiplying $I_{Bias}(t)$ by this parameter produces the result shown by the blue line in Fig. 3 (a). Subtracting this result to $\nabla_y n(x_{Edge}, y_0, t)$, gives $\nabla_y n_T(x_{Edge}, y_0, t) + \delta_E(x_{Edge}, y_0)$ [see Fig. 3 (b), green crosses]. A discontinuity appears due to the uncorrected offset $\delta_E(x_{Edge}, y_0)$ which is

Fig. 3 (a) Example of scaling I_{Bias} at $x_0 = x_{Edge}$ and $y_0 = 15 \mu\text{m}$. (b) Example of the next steps taken to decouple carrier- and temperature-associated gradients at $x_0 = x_{Edge}$ and $y_0 = 15 \mu\text{m}$. (c) Final vertical carrier gradient for different y_0 at $x_0 = x_{Edge}$.

then subtracted to obtain $\nabla_y n_T(x_{Edge}, y_0, t)$ [see Fig. 3 (b), magenta crosses] according to the criteria outlined in III.A. The red line in Fig. 3 (b) represents the fitting of (5) to $\nabla_y n_T(x_{Edge}, y_0, t)$, showing an excellent agreement. Finally, Fig. 3 (b) displays the resulting $\nabla_y n_C(x_{Edge}, y_0, t)$ in blue. To further analyze these results, Fig. 3 (c) presents $\nabla_y C(x_{Edge}, y_0, t)$ waveforms at various (x_{Edge}, y_0) , derived using $(\partial n / \partial C)_T = 3.21 \times 10^{-21} \text{cm}^3$ [11]. Fig. 3 (c) supports the general applicability of this approach. After t_0 , $\nabla_y C(x_{Edge}, y_0, t)$ gradually decreases due to the evolving current injection area at the JTE-drift zone interface. This results from voltage-driven dopant ionization [10], which alters the effective doping concentration along the JTE pn-junction (PiN diode) as the voltage drop increases, stabilizing at t_r . In summary, the results confirm that $K(x_0, y_0)$ and $\delta_E(x_{Edge}, y_0)$ are robust physically-based compensation constants, validating the assumptions performed in III.A.

To assess the correction for the beam's large diameter effect on measurements, $C(x_{Edge}, y_0, t = t_r)$ is extracted. The procedure outlined in Fig. 3 is followed for both the vertical and lateral gradients, which are subsequently integrated along y_0 after multiplying them by $(\partial C / \partial n)_T$. Fig. 5 compares experimental $C(x_{Edge}, y_0, t = t_r)$ with (red squares) and without (black squares) applying the strategy from III.B, to TCAD simulations (blue line) representing the total free-carrier minus the ionized dopant densities (ΔC_{Total}). The deconvolution approach significantly improves agreement between simulations and measurements in the drift zone. However, for $y > 13 \mu\text{m}$, where the n^+ substrate begins, the discrepancy remains, indicating that the convolution is not its cause. Instead, temperature variations

ionize dopants, inducing an additional carrier gradient. To investigate this, simulations have been performed at various power injection levels P . Figs. 6 (a) and 6 (b) show results for $x_0 = x_{Edge}$ and $y = 22 \mu\text{m}$. Fig. 6 (a) illustrates the strong correlation between temperature (T , red dashed line) and ionized donor concentration (N_D , black solid line). Fig. 6 (b) confirms this relationship through $\nabla_y T$ and $\nabla_y N_D$ at the same depth. Fig. 6 (c) further supports this by displaying ΔC_{Total} as a function of y under different power dissipation levels P . As Fig. 6 (c) shows, the free-carrier density varies with depth, confirming for $y > 13 \mu\text{m}$, a carrier density gradient and its dependence on P and in turn, on T .

V. CONCLUSIONS

The use of IIR-LD for determining free-carrier density profiles in WBG power devices has been demonstrated in a 1.2 kV SiC Schottky diode under overcurrent stress. To this end, a novel approach has been presented. First, temperature and carrier concentration effects on the refractive index are decoupled using the current-carrier gradient relationship. Second, a deconvolution technique corrects for the finite laser beam effect on free-carrier gradients ($2 \mu\text{m}$ spatial resolution). In a $13 \mu\text{m}$ -thin drift zone, IIR-LD has been capable of measuring a carrier density profile ranging from 2.73×10^{16} to $3.47 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. TCAD simulations show good agreement, validating the method. Besides, simulations and experiments reveal a temperature-induced carrier gradient in the substrate.

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Fig. 5 Free-carrier concentration measurements before and after deconvolution compared with the TCAD simulations.

Fig. 6 (a) Comparison of temperature and ionized dopant density at $x = x_{Edge}$ and $y = 22 \mu\text{m}$. (b) Comparison of vertical temperature gradient and vertical gradient of ionized donor concentration at $x = x_{Edge}$ and $y = 22 \mu\text{m}$. (c) Simulated ΔC_{Total} profile at $t = t_r$ for different P values.

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